

Developing Spin Coated Nano-Interfaces of Fluorescent Undoped and F-Doped ZnO Quantum Dots

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ABSTRACT

Thin nanostructured films of semiconductor materials are widely applied in various technological devices for next-generation technologies, such as microelectronics, photovoltaics, data storage, and optical and microwave nanodevices. The spin-coating technique is one of the easiest and most valuable strategies for creating thin films onto specific substrates to produce functional 2D nanodevices. However, optimizing the main operative parameters is fundamental in fabricating homogeneous films for optoelectronic, sensing, and other technological applications. Here, we propose a spin-coating protocol to develop nano-interfaces of fluorescent fluorine-doped ZnO quantum dots (QDs), highlighting how the deposition conditions and the choice of the substrate material result are decisive in defining the final structural organization of nanostructured interfaces. The combination of solid-state ellipsometry, x-ray reflectivity (XRR), and photoluminescence led to defining the best conditions to deposit fluorine-doped ZnO QDs onto silicon and glass substrates and to developing fluorescent nano-interfaces with controlled thickness and roughness. The best conditions to obtain a thin nanostructured film with good photoluminescence are guaranteed by a QDs suspension at a concentration equal to 3.0 mg mL⁻¹ and a speed rotation of 3000 rpm using glass supports.

1 | Introduction

Thin films made of optical, electronic, or magnetic materials have been widely used and applied in various technologi-

cal devices for next-generation technologies [1]. Compared to bulk materials, thin films and nano-interfaces can reduce the overall volume of the device and also enhance its properties in many different fields, such as microelectronics, pho-

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tovoltaics, data storage, and optical and microwave devices [2].

Inorganic nanoparticles (NPs) and quantum dots (QDs) have attracted a growing interest because of their peculiar properties [3–7]. They are valuable materials for producing thin films and nanostructured interfaces for many technological applications, including electronics, energy, healthcare, and optics.

Among the materials used to produce functional thin nano-interfaces, transparent conducting zinc oxide (ZnO) is an attractive one thanks to its good chemical, optical, and electrical features combined with low cost, non-toxicity, natural abundance, and easy processability and functionalization [8, 9]. In addition, the inclusion of doping agents has been proposed as a valuable way to improve their physicochemical performances. An intriguing example is the fluorine doping of ZnO crystals to improve the electrical conductivity and fluorescence emission [10–12].

The fabrication methods are decisive in developing thin films and nanostructured interfaces with advanced and controlled physicochemical features to be applied to functional nanodevices. Several techniques have been studied over the years, including electron deposition [13], cold-spray deposition [14], Langmuir-Blodgett technique [15], sol-gel chemistry-based deposition [16], and in situ NP synthesis using polymeric thin films as templates [17]. Although these approaches are widely used for the production of nanostructured interfaces, they also have disadvantages such as high costs, non-scalability of the process, loss of film ductility, and the formation of defects due to the transfer process for the Langmuir-Blodgett method [18–20]. In this context, the spin coating is one of the most rapid and valuable approaches for depositing thin films and for creating nanostructured interfaces on substrates, thanks to many benefits related to their use, such as convenience and relative ease of setting up. Indeed, when a solution of specific substances, such as (macro)molecules or NPs, is quickly spun onto a support, the centripetal force and the liquid's surface tension work together to cover the substrate uniformly [21]. However, many parameters, such as rotation speed and time, amount, and concentration of NPs to be deposited, as well as the chemical nature of the substrate material need to be optimized to obtain a thin and homogeneous nanostructured film.

In this study, a spin coating protocol is proposed to develop nano-interfaces of F-doped ZnO QDs, highlighting how the resulting deposition conditions are decisive in obtaining thin nanostructured films. The combination of solid-state ellipsometry, x-ray reflectivity (XRR), and photoluminescence analyses allows for the investigation of the role of the spin-coating protocol and deposition parameters to modulate the thickness and roughness of thin nanostructured interfaces, simultaneously preserving the fluorescence emission of constituting QDs. This study aims to propose a valuable strategy through which developing nano-biointerfaces based on semiconductor nanocrystals for technological applications, such as optoelectronics as well as optical sensing.

2 | Experimental Section

2.1 | Synthesis of ZnO-Based QDs

Undoped and F-doped (nominal concentration of doping agent equal to 5 at. %) zinc oxide QDs (F/ZnO QDs) were synthesized through a wet-precipitation method as previously described, whose main physicochemical properties, such as average radius (R), maximum absorption (λ_{abs}), energy band-gap (E_g), and relative quantum yield (Φ), are summarized in Table 1 [12]. The synthesized QDs were stored in methanol at a concentration of 3.0 mg mL⁻¹ to be used in fabricating thin nano-interfaces.

2.2 | Preparation of Nanostructured Interfaces by Spin-Coating

The spin coating technique was adopted in the preparation of thin nano-interfaces of ZnO-based QDs [21, 22], and a four-step procedure including (i) QDs deposition, (ii) spin-up, (iii) spin-off, and (iv) solvent evaporation was used (Figure 1). Two different kinds of support, such as glass or silicon wafers, were used to produce the thin nano-interfaces by using the same spin-coating protocol. The centrifugal force facilitates the distribution of the solution on the support and the evaporation of the solvent.

Finally, each support was also heated at 70°C, which is a value slightly above the boiling temperature of methanol to achieve a complete evaporation of the solvent. Different spinning conditions were tested in terms of concentration of QDs in methanol suspension (0.5, 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0 mg mL⁻¹) and rotation speed (1000, 2000, 3000, and 4000 rpm), while the time was set to 60 s.

2.3 | Solid-State Ellipsometry Analysis

Ellipsometry is an optical technique that allows the detection of the variation of the polarization state of a polarized light beam produced by interaction with a linear optical element. Only the change in the polarization state between incident and reflected wave is measured making the measurement independent of the intensity of the beam and then by any fluctuations of the intensity [23, 24].

Solid-state ellipsometry measurements were carried out at PCSM laboratories in Grenoble (France) by using a fixed angle of incidence (75°) homemade instrument consisting of a red laser, a retarder plate, and two polarizers (<https://pscm-grenoble.eu/equipments/>). The first one is placed between the source and the sample to further polarize the incident light, while the second one is placed between the sample and the detector to analyze the polarization of reflected light. Measurements were first performed on cleaned silicon supports to determine their oxide thickness, thanks to the use of Ellipsometer software (<https://www.semiconsoft.com/wp2/tfcompanion-thickness>), using the silicon oxide's refractive index = 1.4650, considering a wavelength

TABLE 1 | Physicochemical parameters of undoped and F-doped ZnO QDs [12].

ZnO QDs	R (nm)	λ_{abs} (nm)	E_g (eV)	Φ (%)
Undoped	3.0 ± 1.0	339	3.31 ± 0.01	7 ± 1
F-doped	3.0 ± 0.8	343	3.27 ± 0.01	22 ± 2

FIGURE 1 | Schematic representation of the spin-coating procedure to produce ZnO-based nano-interfaces.

of 633 nm, and then on nanostructured films on at least 20 analysis points per substrate.

2.4 | XRR Analysis

Reflectivity techniques analyze the reflective radiation from surfaces. In a typical experiment, the property of a flat surface to reflect the incoming wave, thus scattering it at the same incident angle, is exploited. By measuring reflected wave intensity over the incident one, as a function of the scattering vector \mathbf{q} , some information about the composition normal to the sample surface can be obtained [25]. XRR was performed to analyze the thickness and roughness of nanostructured films on silicon and glass supports. XRR measurements were carried out at the PCSM laboratories in Grenoble (France), by using a PANalytical Empyrean instrument with a copper (Cu) source. After several tests, the best final configuration for the characterization of F/ZnO nano-interfaces was fixed as follows: 10 mm Cu mask, defining the incoming beam width, $1/32^\circ$ slit for incident beam height and divergence, $1/4^\circ$ anti-scattering slit after the sample, and $1/8^\circ$ slit in front of the detector, no soller, and automatic attenuator.

2.5 | Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM images were acquired to investigate the morphological feature of undoped and F-doped ZnO thin nanostructured films using the FEI Nova NanoSEM450 instrument. The

images were carried out at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV by collecting secondary electrons with an ETD detector [26].

2.6 | Photoluminescence analysis

Photoluminescence measurements were carried out at CEA-Leti Research and Technology Institute (Grenoble, France) using a Horiba LabRAM HR instrument, equipped with a microscope objective (x40, Thorlabs NA 0.5 WD 1 mm), a visible grating (100 grooves/mm), and CCD detector. The measurements were performed using a laser with a wavelength of 325 nm, power of 1 mW at room temperature, and with an entrance of 300 μm . The emission spectra were collected in the 330–930 nm range.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Structural Properties of the Nano-Interfaces: The Role of the Spin-Coating Parameters

The effect of the speed rotation on the formation and the structural properties of nanostructured films was analyzed by depositing specific amounts of the QDs suspension at 3.0 mg mL⁻¹ on the silicon supports at two different rotation speeds, such as 1000 and 3000 rpm, as shown in Figure 2.

A first qualitative analysis showed that the films obtained using a speed rotation of 1000 rpm (Figure 2A,C) were more heteroge-

TABLE 2 | Thickness values for undoped and F-doped ZnO nanostructured interfaces deposited on the silicon supports.

Speed rotation (rpm)	Thickness of nano-interfaces (nm)	
	Undoped ZnO	F-doped ZnO
1000	30 ± 9	33 ± 7
3000	13 ± 1	19 ± 1

TABLE 3 | Thickness values for undoped and F/ZnO nanostructured interfaces on silicon supports were obtained alternatively using QDs suspensions at different concentrations.

QDs concentration (mg mL ⁻¹)	Thickness of nano-interfaces (nm)	
	Undoped ZnO	F-doped ZnO
3.0	13 ± 1	19 ± 1
2.0	9 ± 1	12 ± 1
1.0	7 ± 1	8 ± 1
0.5	7 ± 1	8 ± 1

FIGURE 2 | Photos of undoped (A and B) and F-doped (C and D) ZnO nanostructured interfaces deposited on silicon supports by spin-coating using a speed rotation of 1000 rpm (A and C) or 3000 rpm (B and D), respectively.

neous than those obtained using a speed rotation of 3000 rpm (Figure 2B,D). The average values of the nanofilm's thickness, as summarized in Table 2, were estimated by performing ellipsometry measurements on at least 20 different points for each sample.

The quantitative analysis confirmed that both nano-interfaces obtained with a 3000 rpm speed rotation resulted in a more homogeneous and thinner than those obtained with a lower speed rotation. Then, the speed rotation was fixed at 3000 rpm to test the effect of the concentration of QDs suspension, such as 3.0, 2.0, 1.0, and 0.5 mg mL⁻¹, on the thickness of the produced thin films. As reported in Table 3 and Figure 3, average thickness values of about 7–8 nm were estimated at low QDs concentration

FIGURE 3 | Thickness values as a function of QDs concentration of undoped (blue triangles) and F-doped (green rhombus) ZnO nanostructured interfaces by spin-coating at 3000 rpm onto silicon supports.

(0.5 and 1.0 mg mL⁻¹), which tend to increase at higher concentrations.

Based on these results, the lowest concentrations of QDs suspensions were preferred while the speed rotation was further increased to 4000 rpm to obtain ZnO nano-interfaces as thin as possible. As shown in Table 4, the estimated average thickness values indicated that the increase in speed rotation did not reduce the thickness of the nanostructured interfaces. These preliminary analyses confirmed that a good nanostructured interface was obtainable using QDs suspension at low concentrations (0.5 or 1.0 mg mL⁻¹) and high-speed rotation (3000 or 4000 rpm). Nevertheless, the analysis of the nanointerfaces produced onto glass support was not realized by solid-state ellipsometry due to the back reflection from the lower face of the support

TABLE 4 | Thickness values of the nanostructured interfaces composed of undoped and F-doped ZnO QDs obtained on silicon support using a speed rotation of 4000 rpm.

QD concentration (mg mL ⁻¹)	Thickness of nano-interfaces (nm)	
	Undoped ZnO	F-doped ZnO
1.0	8 ± 1	9 ± 1
0.5	7 ± 1	7 ± 1

FIGURE 4 | Experimental R data as a function of q_z (red circles) and its best fit curve (black line) (A). SLD profile plotted as a function of distance Z (red line) (B) of the nano-interface on silicon support.

TABLE 5 | Values of the structural parameters, such as thickness (T), roughness (R), and scattering length density (SLD), estimated by the best fitting of XRR profiles for the nanointerface produced on the silicon support.

Layer	T (nm)	R (nm)	SLD (10^{-4} nm^{-2})
Si		0.50 ± 0.07	2.00 ± 0.02
SiO ₂	2.11 ± 0.01	0.50 ± 0.09	1.90 ± 0.02
ZnO	1.54 ± 0.06	0.36 ± 0.01	1.37 ± 0.02

significantly affecting the determination of the nano-interface's thickness.

At this time, XRR measurements were also performed on the nanointerface samples obtained by spin-coating at the lower concentration of QDs suspension (0.5 mg mL⁻¹) and speed rotation of 3000 rpm to finely define their structural properties.

The reflectivity R as a function of the scattering vector q_z and the resulting scattering length density (SLD) profile were plotted in Figure 4A and Figure 4B, respectively. SLD is a measure of the scattering power of a material. For x-rays, the scattering length of an atom is roughly proportional to the atomic number Z of that atom. Considering that the silicon support consists of Si/SiO₂, the best fit of the experimental data leads to the estimation of the values of the structural parameters, such as thickness T , roughness R , and scattering length density SLD, as reported in Table 5. The fitting was carried out with a two-layer model. The first layer represents the SiO₂ layer on the top of the silicon support, and the second layer represents the ZnO QDs.

A deeper analysis of the SLD profile and the higher value of the thickness of the ZnO compared to the NP radius suggested that the support surface was not completely covered by the film of QDs. Consequently, although the measurements of solid-state ellipsometry showed that low concentrations of QD suspensions were sufficient to create a film covering the entire support, XRR analysis indicated that nonetheless, support coverage was incomplete. For this reason, the optimal conditions to realize the nanostructured interfaces by spin coated were fixed to the higher QDs concentration of 3 mg mL⁻¹ keeping constant the speed rotation at 3000 rpm to obtain homogeneously and fully covered silicon and glass supports.

3.2 | Structural Properties of the Nano-Interfaces: The Role of the Support Type

Together with the spin coating parameters, the choice of the appropriate support on which to deposit the QDs is a decisive step to obtaining homogeneous nanostructured films [27]. For this reason, both undoped and F-doped QD suspensions at 3 mg mL⁻¹ were deposited on both silicon and glass supports using

FIGURE 5 | XRR experimental data (circles) and the best fit (black line) of undoped ZnO QDs on silicon (A), and on glass (B) supports, and of F-doped ZnO QDs on silicon (C), and on glass (D) supports. The corresponding SLD curves are shown in the inserts.

a speed rotation of 3000 rpm. By qualitatively comparing the XRR profiles (Figure 5), it is possible to note that for both QD types, the nanointerfaces appeared quite different as a function of the chemical nature of the two supports. To quantitatively compare the structural properties of such nano-interfaces onto different supports, the XRR profiles were fitted. As reported in Figure 5 and Table 6, the XRR data of the nanostructured films on glass support (Figure 5A,C) were fitted considering a single layer of QDs, while a two-layer model was used for those on silicon supports (Figure 5B,D).

The data reported in Table 6 indicated that, for both undoped and F-doped ZnO QDs, two layers of different thickness and roughness were obtained on silicon support, while a single layer was produced on the glass support. In both cases of silicon-supported nano-interfaces, the first layer, which was closer to the support surface, was thinner and more homogeneous than the second one. In addition, the thickness values of the second layer estimated by XRR were identical to those obtained through solid-state ellipsometry. In contrast, in the case of glass supports, a single layer with a thickness of about 10.5 and 13.7 nm and a roughness of about 2.42 and 3.56 nm were obtained for undoped and F-doped ZnO nano-interfaces, respectively. Therefore, these results confirmed that the formation of two QDs layers with heterogeneous thickness and roughness was produced onto silicon supports, while a more homoge-

nous nanostructured nano-interface was realized onto glass supports.

SEM measurements were conducted better to visualize the morphology of QDs-based nano-interfaces. As can be seen from Figure 6, in both cases, the QDs completely cover the support, although the film obtained by dispersing the ZnO QDs appears more homogeneous and less rough than that obtained from the suspension of F-ZnO QDs. These images, therefore, confirm the thickness and roughness values obtained by fitting the reflectivity data.

3.3 | Photoluminescence of F/ZnO Nano-Interfaces

To exploit the produced nano-interfaces as potential 2D optical nanodevices, the photoluminescence behavior was assessed. As shown in Figure 7, both undoped and F-doped materials emitted under laser irradiation, generating a characteristic photoluminescence spectrum composed of a well-defined peak at ~ 380 nm and a broad band in the range of 450–750 nm.

The first peak was ascribed to near-band-edge excitonic transitions of free carriers from the valence band to the conduction one, while the broad yellow-green band [28] was mainly ascribable

TABLE 6 | Values of the parameters obtained by the best fitting of XRR data for both the undoped and F-doped ZnO QDs on silicon and glass supports.

Nano-interfaces	Layer	T (nm)	R (nm)	SLD (10^{-4} nm^{-2})
Undoped ZnO on silicon support	Si		0.2 ± 0.1	1.89 ± 0.09
	SiO ₂	1.45 ± 0.02	0.28 ± 0.01	1.98 ± 0.08
	ZnO_1	7.26 ± 0.05	1.68 ± 0.06	3.16 ± 0.07
	ZnO_2	15 ± 2	5.9 ± 0.8	2.0 ± 0.1
Undoped ZnO on glass support	Glass		0.36 ± 0.01	2.29 ± 0.04
	ZnO	10.5 ± 0.1	2.42 ± 0.05	3.22 ± 0.05
F-doped ZnO on silicon support	Si		0.1 ± 0.1	1.89 ± 0.09
	SiO ₂	0.4 ± 0.2	0.25 ± 0.03	2.15 ± 0.05
	ZnO_1	11.2 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 0.2	3.22 ± 0.06
	ZnO_2	14 ± 3	8.6 ± 1.4	2.4 ± 0.2
F-doped ZnO on glass support	Glass		0.10 ± 0.06	2.09 ± 0.01
	ZnO	13.7 ± 0.1	3.56 ± 0.05	2.52 ± 0.01

FIGURE 7 | Photoluminescence spectra of undoped and F-doped ZnO, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 325 \text{ nm}$ (A).

to the presence of surface defects, such as oxygen vacancies (V_o) and interstitial oxygen (O_i), as well as other defects like zinc vacancies (V_{zn}) or interstitial zinc (Zn_i), all representing the photoluminescence centers directly related to the emission [29–31]. The intensity of the band at about 380 nm was similar for

both undoped and F-doped samples, indicating that no significant changes were induced by the fluorine doping to the near-band-edge transitions of zinc oxide. On the contrary, the intensity of the visible bands was not the same for the two nanomaterials. Indeed, considering that this depended on the number of luminescence centers and the recombination of the electron-hole pairs [32, 33], the obtained results may indicate that the fluorine doping agent tends to modify the point defects within the crystalline structure of ZnO, partially occupying the oxygen vacancies, thus leading to an increase in the photoluminescence intensity of the final nano-interfaces. This evidence confirmed the previously obtained fluorescence results for ZnO and F/ZnO QDs in solution [12].

4 | Conclusions

This study aimed to develop fluorescent thin nano-interfaces of F-doped ZnO QDs through a spin-coating strategy by optimizing the main operative parameters, such as speed rotation, concentration of QDs suspension, and substrate nature, which was decisive in fabricating homogeneous nanostructured thin films for photo-sensing and optoelectronic applications. Low concentrations of QDs suspension and high rotation speeds led to the formation of thin films, as confirmed by solid-state ellipsometry results, but they were not sufficient to totally cover the silicon substrate, as

demonstrated by XRR analysis. Therefore, the best conditions to avoid these limits were guaranteed by a concentration of QDs suspension equal to 3.0 mg mL^{-1} and a speed rotation of 3000 rpm. The chemical nature of the substrate (i.e., silicon or glass) was also decisive in producing thin and homogeneous nanostructured interfaces. Indeed, by using the same spin-coating protocol, two layers of QDs with different thicknesses and roughness were obtained on silicon supports, while a single layer of QDs was produced onto glass one as demonstrated by ellipsometry and XRR analyses. In both cases of the nano-interfaces of F-doped ZnO, the layer closer to the silicon or glass surface was very thin (11–13 nm) with low roughness (2–3 nm) and homogeneously deposited onto the whole substrate. These obtained nano-interfaces showed a high fluorescence emission, as confirmed by photoluminescence results, due to the quantum confinement character of QDs as well as to the structural defects also induced by fluorine atomic doping, which were not altered after the deposition into nanostructured films. Definitely, this work has therefore shown how spin-coating could represent a useful and easy strategy to produce thin nano-interfaces of fluorescent F/ZnO QDs as further main components of optical nanodevices.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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